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Germany's forest cluster: exploratory spatial data analysis of regional agglomerations and structural change in wood-based employment – Primary wood processing

Cluster Wald und Holz Deutschland: Explorative Raumdatenanalyse von regionalen Schwerpunkten und strukturellem Wandel in der Holz-basierten Beschäftigung – Holz bearbeitende Industrie

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Abstract

The 'forest cluster' unites all industries that maintain a close relationship to their common raw material wood and therewith to the forest. A growing research in Europe's national forest clusters suggests a considerable contribution of wood-based supply chains to employment, yet lacks a true regional science perspective on their distribution and trends in space. This study proposes an approach for consistent targeting of the forest sector on different spatial scales, which combines a sectoral forest cluster definition, a regional shift-share analysis and an exploratory spatial data analysis (ESDA) based on geostatistical cluster indices. A German case study demonstrates its capacity to assess the sector's position and trends in the national economy, depict structural changes on regional scales and contributes to gaining insight into local spatial dynamics of wood-based employment. The German forest cluster ranks high among other producing industries, but shows a disproportional decline in employment. The group of primary wood processing industries (sawmilling, wood-based panels) reveals diverging employment trends in declining western federal states and moderately growing eastern federal states. County-level employment maps draw a detailed picture of spatial concentration dynamics and outstanding clustering regions, which can be linked to locational factors influencing their geographic location, size and regional significance. The research contributes to an improved empirical understanding of the forest sector in macro- and regional economics.

Key words: forest sector, forest cluster, wood supply chain, regional industrial clusters, macroeconomics, shift-share analysis, geostatistics

Kurzfassung

Der Cluster Wald und Holz vereint all diejenigen Wirtschaftszweige, die einen engen Bezug zum Rohstoff Holz und damit zum Wald aufweisen. Eine wachsende Forschung zu Europas nationalen Forstsektoren legt eine beträchtliche Bedeutung der Holz basierten Wertschöpfungsketten für die Beschäftigung nahe, entbehrt aber bislang einer echten regionalwissenschaftlichen Perspektive auf ihre Ausprägung und Trends im Raum. Im vorliegenden Artikel wird ein Ansatz für eine konsistente Strukturierung des Forstsektors auf verschiedenen räumlichen Ebenen vorgestellt, der eine sektorale Clusterdefinition, eine regionale Shift-Share-Analyse und eine explorative Raumdatenanalyse (ESDA) basierend auf geostatistischen Clusterindizes vereint. Die Fallstudie Deutschland verdeutlicht die Leistungsfähigkeit des Verfahrens, den Forstsektor und seine Trends im gesamtwirtschaftlichen Kontext erfassen, den strukturellen Wandel auf der regionalen Ebene abbilden und einen Einblick in die räumliche Dynamik der Holz-bezogenen Beschäftigung gewinnen zu können. Der Cluster Wald und Holz nimmt einen hohen Stellenwert innerhalb des Produzierenden Gewerbes ein, zeigt jedoch überproportionale Arbeitsplatzverluste. Die primären Holz verarbeitenden Industrien (Sägewerke, Holzwerkstoffindustrie) lassen allerdings regional unterschiedliche Trends zwischen stark zurückgehender Beschäftigung im Westen und schwach wachsenden Arbeitsplätzen im Osten erkennen. Beschäftigungskarten auf Landkreisebene liefern ein detailliertes Bild der räumlichen Konzentrationsdynamik und ausgeprägter Clusterregionen, die in Bezug zu spezifischen Regionalfaktoren gesetzt werden können, welche die räumliche Lage, Größe und regionale Bedeutung beeinflussen. Die Forschung trägt so zu einem verbesserten empirischen Verständnis des Cluster Wald und Holz aus volkswirtschaftlicher und regional-ökonomischer Sicht bei.

Schlüsselwörter: Forstsektor, Cluster Wald und Holz, Wertschöpfungskette Holz, regionale Industrie-Cluster, Makroökonomie, Shift-Share-Analyse, Geostatistik

Introduction

Perceiving the forest sector as a cluster of related industries (Porter 2000) has become the focus of an emerging research in forest sciences. The *forest cluster* (Lammi 1996) incorporates raw timber producing forestry enterprises, processing industries of semi-finished wood, pulp and paper products and downstream manufacturing industries that provide various finished wood and paper products to end consumers. These industries maintain a close relationship to their com-

mon raw material wood and reveal high connectivity along regional supply chains. Clearly, employment and growth in these industries show a direct linkage to and high dependency on the resource wood and therewith to the forest (European Commission 1999).

The view of one large forest sector was put forward by the European Union to promote a common strategy for sustainable development of one of its largest industrial sectors. The cluster contributes decisively to socioeconomic sustainability by providing opportunities for value adding and employment on the basis of a regenerative natu-

ral resource. In view of global trends such as population growth, climate change, growing energy needs and increasingly scarce resources, the *wood supply chain* offers considerable strengths and opportunities for the sustainable development of rural areas and forest-dependant regions (EUROFOR 1994, 1997, Blombäck et al. 2003, UNECE/FAO 2005, Becker et al. 2007, Schulte 2007).

The research yields a variety of case studies focused on regional economics of the sector (Viitamo 2001, refer to Kies (2008) for a comprehensive literature overview). In the North-American context, numerous studies exist since the 1980's (e. g. Flick et al. 1980, Marchak 1983, Aruna et al. 1997, Abt et al. 2002). However, only recently a sectoral perspective of forest industries is gaining in importance in the United States and more cases of industrial wood clusters are documented (NRC-CFS 2006, Wear et al. 2007, Young et al. 2007, Aguilar 2008, Aguilar et al. 2009). In Europe, early comparative studies (EUROFOR 1994, 1997, Hazley 2000) induced more detailed investigations in individual countries, some of which have subsequently established individual governmental reporting schemes on the forest sector (e. g. Hanzl and Urban 2000, Eder et al. 2004, BUWAL 2004, MEIE 2008, Skogsindustrierna 2000, CEBR 2006, Kokkonen and Hytönen 2006).

In Germany, the term forest cluster (in German: *Cluster Wald und Holz*) initially emerged from a large-scale survey in the State of North Rhine-Westphalia, which revealed an unforeseen impact of the forest sector on employment in the highly industrialized federal state (Schulte 2002, 2003, Schulte and Mrosek 2006). Following this example, independent studies investigated the sector in nearly all federal states (e. g. Seegmüller 2005, Kramer and Möller 2006, Jaensch and Harsche 2007, Rüter et al. 2007, Röder et al. 2008, Klein et al. 2009b, c). Likewise a sparse, misleading information basis for the whole German federal republic led to several national level studies (Dieter and Thoroe 2003, Mrosek et al. 2005, BMELV 2008, Kies et al. 2008).

Across various contexts and scales, the studies commonly recognize the important role of the forest sector for employment in both national and regional economies, which is frequently higher than previously anticipated. However, the studies often relate to incongruent definitions, sources and methodologies that lead to inconsistent, barely comparable results among studied cases and contexts. So far the research has focused on global structures and trends, but it still lacks a true regional science perspective on the forest cluster's distribution in space.

This research aims at strengthening the knowledge on the socio-economic role of industrial activities that are linked to the primary resource wood originating from forest ecosystems. It assumes that forest-based employment as a whole contributes considerably to the national economy, yet that its spatial distribution and trends are not ubiquitous and uniform but characterized by outstanding concentrations in particular regions. Motivated by the obvious lack of consistent methodologies for forest sector analysis on different spatial scales, its objective is to specify an approach for (geo)statistical assessment of employment in Germany's forest sector, that is suitable for industrial targeting, benchmarking and regular monitoring of its economic development. The empirical aims are to (i) measure the sector's position in the overall economy, (ii) depict trends and structural changes of the sector and its branches on national and regional scales and (iii) gain insight into spatial patterns of wood-based employment and the hypothetical existence of regional industrial clusters.

This paper presents findings from research at the Wald-Zentrum, University of Münster, since 2004. It builds on earlier publications by the authors, notably Kies et al. (2008, 2009) and Klein et al. (2009a), but contains further updated data, a longer time series and more in-depth spatial analysis. Being the first part of a series of consecutive publications on the German forest cluster, this paper focuses on primary wood processing industries.

Methods

Forest cluster definition and macroeconomics

Wood-based industries are allocated to separate sections of the statistical Nomenclature of Economic Activities in the European Community (NACE) (EUROSTAT 2002) (e. g. forestry in A 'agriculture', wood and paper industries in D 'manufacturing', carpentry in F 'construction'). No class for the total forest sector as such is specified, which is why it has to be defined as an aggregate collection of selected classes. Owing to diverse understandings of the sector, the existing case studies reveal numerous dissimilar definitions that include or omit particular wood-based classes.

Kies et al. (2008) develops a forest cluster definition for Germany (Table 1), which borrows from the original EU concept (European Commission 1999) and extends many of the rather narrow definitions used in previous case studies. The total forest cluster is a construct of NACE classes that show a clear linkage to the primary resource wood (content) and are covered through regular re-

Table 1. Structure of employment in Germany's forest cluster 2008. Sources: EUROSTAT (2002), Kies et al. (2008), BA (2008), StBA (2008). Struktur der Beschäftigung im Cluster Wald und Holz Deutschland 2008.

Industries (NACE), sub-sector, cluster aggregates	Employees		
	(1,000)	(%)	(per enterprise)*
Forestry (02)	18.0	2	3.9
Solid wood subsector			
Wood products (20.1)	136.4	16	6.9
Sawmilling (20.1)	29.0	3	8.0
Wood-based panels (20.2)	15.4	2	53.9
Wood construction (20.3)	61.5	7	5.6
Wood packaging (20.4)	11.2	1	14.4
Misc. wood products (20.5)	19.3	2	4.8
Furniture (36.1)	136.8	16	11.7
Wood crafts (45x) ¹	115.4	13	3.0
Carpentry (45.22.3)	52.1	6	4.4
Joinery (45.42)	58.4	7	2.5
Paquet laying (45.43.1)	4.9	1	2.2
Wood trade (5x) ²	12.1	1	3.4
<i>subtotal</i>	400.7	47	6.1
Cellulose sub-sector			
Paper products (21)	131.5	15	48.2
Paper production (21.1)	54.3	6	85.7
Paper articles (21.2)	77.2	9	37.1
Publishing, printing (22)	306.9	36	12.1
Publishing (22.1)	134.7	16	14.0
Printing (22.2)	172.2	20	11.5
<i>subtotal</i>	438.4	51	15.6
Cluster total	857.2	100	8.6
Cluster in producing industries ³	827.0	96	8.5
Cluster excluding 22	550.3	64	7.4

Note: ¹aggregate, not part of NACE; ²aggregate, includes 51.53.2 wholesale of wood, 51.53.3 wholesale of wood products, 52.44.6 retail sale of wood; ³excludes NACE 02 and 52x; *relates to the number of enterprises as of the value-added tax statistics 2007 (StBA 2009)

porting in official statistical information systems (data availability). For benchmarking of the sector's macroeconomic size, trends and relative position, it permits a consistent comparison to the national economy (NACE A-O) and the producing industries (NACE C-F) as referential classes.

The forest cluster definition relates to the Statistics of employees with social insurance registration (employment statistics) [Statistik der sozialversicherungspflichtig Beschäftigten] (BA 2008), Germany's official labour market information system. The source provides complete and reproducible information from national to local scale, even on lower levels of the NACE hierarchy. Compared to other statistical sources, such as the producing industries statistics [Statistik des Produzierenden Gewerbes], which survey only plants with more than 20 employees, their advantage is a more complete mapping of the predominantly small scale forest sector. They also permit to consider small craft and trade industries (which have been assessed through disconnected surveys) without losing the benchmarking properties of the referential NACE system. Further explanations and a systematic evaluation of the statistics' capabilities can be found in Kies et al. (2008).

Regional shift-share analysis

Shift-share analysis is a standard analytical tool for exploratory targeting of regional employment dynamics (Dinc et al. 1998, Stimson et al. 2006). It extends relative trend analysis and allows identifying regional growth (or decline) that can be traced back to competitive locational factors. The fundamental assumption is that a region's growth is influenced by the overall economy, but that locational factors might play a decisive role in diverging regional trends. The conventional model decomposes a region's total shift in employment observed over a defined time interval into three components (Formula 1):

$$\Delta e_{ir} = \underbrace{e_{ir}^t \left(\frac{e_n^{t+1}}{e_n^t} - 1 \right)}_{\text{total shift}} + \underbrace{e_{ir}^t \left(\frac{e_{in}^{t+1}}{e_{in}^t} - \frac{e_n^{t+1}}{e_n^t} \right)}_{\text{national share}} + \underbrace{e_{ir}^t \left(\frac{e_{ir}^{t+1}}{e_{ir}^t} - \frac{e_{in}^{t+1}}{e_{in}^t} \right)}_{\text{industrial mix}} + \underbrace{e_{ir}^t \left(\frac{e_{ir}^{t+1}}{e_{ir}^t} - \frac{e_{in}^{t+1}}{e_{in}^t} \right)}_{\text{regional share}} \quad (1)$$

with e = employment, n = reference area (nation),
 i = industry, t = reference point in time (starting year),
 r = region, $t+1$ = comparison point in time (end year).

The *national share* (NS) measures the expected change within a region that can be attributed to the influence of the general economic trend. The *industrial mix* (IM) measures the share of regional growth induced by the trend that is specific to that industry, which hints at a region's industrial specialisation. The *regional share* (RS) measures the growth component that is disconnected from general or industry specific trends and relates to regional growth factors. It allows to identify competitive regions and to estimate the scale of locational factors in relation to other regions or overall economic trends. Further details of the method are explained in Klein et al. (2009a).

Local spatial econometrics

Various econometric coefficients have been applied in the study of concentration, agglomeration or clustering of industries. However, these terms are often used interchangeably in a somewhat diffuse manner. The fundamental difference between standard regional economic indices versus spatial econometrics is their neglect (respectively consideration) of spatial relationships in observations. A-spatial indices neglect geographical dimensions and measure a single local unit's deviation from the global mean, which is defined as *concentration*, regardless of its location in space (e. g. a well-known targeting

tool is the location quotient). However, local units indicating concentrations may be more or less evenly distributed as isolated spots across the global space (dispersion) or, alternatively, be grouped in proximity within one or more regions (clustering). Such a regional deviation of an industry from an average global trend has been defined as *agglomeration* (Arbia 2001, Lafortcade and Mion 2007).

To assess such regional patterns, geospatial autocorrelation statistics such as Moran's I and Getis-Ord G offer suitable methods, which can account for the impacts of neighbouring local units in a geographical space (Anselin 1988, 1995, Getis and Ord 1992, Ord and Getis 1995: Formulae 2, 3). Space is conceptualized here by means of a spatial weights matrix that encodes the units' neighbourhood relationships. Based on this model, the indices measure the level of autocorrelation for each local unit in relation to its neighbours. The resulting spatial pattern is evaluated for statistical significance based on so-called randomised permutation tests that yield pseudo significance levels. Refer to Anselin (1995) and Smith et al. (2008) for explanations of the geostatistical method and to Kies et al. (2009) for details on the specific setup of the analysis in this research.

$$\text{Local Moran's I} \quad I_{i(d)} = x_i \sum_j w_{ij(d)} x_j \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Local } G_i^* \quad G_{i(d)}^* = \frac{\sum_j w_{ij(d)} x_j}{\sum_j x_j} \quad (3)$$

with i, j = indices of local units ($i = j$),
 d = neighbourhood threshold distance,
 x = standardized z-value for local activity,
 w_{ij} = spatial distance weights matrix.

The advantages of spatial econometrics in cluster research are their potential for deeper local analyses in true spatial dimensions. Incorporated into Geographical Information Systems (GIS), they offer powerful tools to visually explore large spatial datasets and identify complex structures or change patterns at a regional to local scale. A particular strength is the explicit assessment of the patterns' statistical significance, which enhances the cartographic visualisation and permits to confirm or reject subjective visual assessments of spatial concentrations in simple mapping procedures.

Analysis outline

The analyses are based on a comprehensive dataset of the German employment statistics (BA 2008), which covers the number of employees (with social insurance registration) in all defined industries of the cluster on the national (federal), regional (state) and local level (county) in a time series from 1994 to 2008. First, the cluster's global structure and predominant trend are analysed in the context of the overall economy. Second, the regional dynamics of the primary wood processing industries (NACE 20.1 sawmilling, 20.2 wood-based panels), a core segment in the cluster's regional wood supply chains, are compared among the federal states by means of the shift-share method and changes in their size structure are investigated. Third, spatial agglomeration trends of these industries are explored cartographically by applying geostatistical cluster indices. Finally, the results are discussed relating to structural peculiarities and locational factors in the regions.

Results

The sector's contribution to national employment

Germany's forest cluster shows a diverse structure of its *three 'sub-sectors' forestry, solid wood and cellulose* (Table 1). The forestry enterprises, representing the initial link in the wood chain, account only for minor shares in employment (2%) (Note: NACE 02 includes only private forestry enterprises, but excludes state and community forestry, which are part of NACE 'administration'). The group of solid wood-based industries accounts for over 400,000 employees or 47%. The largest segments are wood products and furniture (16% each). The cellulose-based industries unite over 438,000 employees (51%), of which 307,000 belong to printing and publishing. The forest sector is generally dominated by *small-to-medium-sized enterprises* (SME): Besides a few typical large scale branches, e. g. NACE 20.2 wood-based panels or NACE 21.1 paper production, the majority of industries is characterised by an average of less than 20 employees per enterprise, and in several branches of even less than 5 employees per enterprise (forestry, crafts, trade).

The cluster's aggregated figures indicate the *macroeconomic size of the sector as a whole*. In 2008 the cluster unites more than 857,000 employees with social insurance registration. 96% belong to the producing industries (NACE C-F). Publishing and printing, which are considered as forest-based industries under the European definition, take a large share of the cluster (36%). Because their linkages to wood resources remain a debated question, an aggregated class excluding NACE 22 branches is also specified: nevertheless, this forest cluster in the narrow sense still accounts for not less than 550,000 employees.

The cluster's *position within the German economy* figures 3.1% of national employment in 2008. The cluster in the producing industries counts 9.5%. A comparison to 13 other sectors puts this figure into perspective (Figure 1). In terms of employment, the forest sector is nearly as important as transport equipment, i. e. the automobile industry and its suppliers (10.2%), clearly larger than food products (7.6%) and ranks on 6th position of all producing industries. Excluding the publishing and printing segment, the cluster (6.3%) still exceeds a number of industries, such as chemicals (5.2%), plastics (4.4%), energy (3.0%), textiles or mining (< 2%).

Figure 1. Relative ranking of the German forest cluster among other sectors by their share of employment of total producing industries (NACE C-F) in 2008.

Relative Rangposition des deutschen ClusterWald und Holz unter anderen Sektoren anhand des Anteils der Beschäftigung am gesamten produzierenden Gewerbe (NACE C-F) im Jahr 2008.

Long-term global employment trends

Time-series analysis from 1994-2008 depicts *three distinct periods* (Figure 2). In early 1994-2000, moderate negative trends prevail in the forest cluster and the wood products segment, which follow the tendency in the producing industries (-12%), while employment stagnates in the national economy (-1%). The two primary wood processing industries under study reveal opposite trends during this period: the sawmill industry indicates stronger losses (-19%), while the wood-based panel industry develops slightly positive. In 2000 however, the national trend turns negative, followed by considerable job losses in the forest sector as part of an overall recession. Over the 2000 to 2006 years, employment losses intensify and a constant decline marks all industries. The wood products segment shows a decline of over -25%, with comparable trends in sawmilling and wood-based panels. These trends occur to be stronger than in the producing industries (-15%) and increasingly deviate from the declining national economy (-5%). Following the 2005 national trend reversal, the decline only comes to an end during 2006-2008: weak positive growth reoccurs in the producing industries and the overall economy (3-4%), while the forest cluster and the wood industries under study stagnate.

The complete 1994-2008 period portrays an *on-going structural change in the forest sector*, revealing a pronounced loss of employees (Table 1, Figure 3). A strong decline in absolute and relative figures occurs in wood products (-65,000, -32%), which also decline in the number of enterprises (-5,500, -22%), reflecting strong competition and concentration processes. The sawmill industry loses more than -1,000 enterprises (-23%) and close to -15,000 employees (-34%). Their average number of employees per enterprise decreases moderately (1994: 9.3, 2008: 8.0, -14%). The wood-based panel industry declines insignificantly in enterprises (-29, -9%), but considerably in employees (-6,400, -29%). A decrease in average employees per enterprise describes the continuous concentration of these industries (1994: 69.3, 2008: 54.8, -21%). The depicted trends in wood-based employment far exceed the national trend (-3%), but can be partly attributed to general tendencies in the producing industries (-22%).

Figure 2. Global employment trends in Germany's forest cluster and the primary wood processing industries, 1994-2008 (1994 = 100). Classificatory shift from earlier NACE 1970 to NACE Rev. 1.1: 1994-1999 data is rescaled for comparability. Globale Beschäftigungstrends im deutschen ClusterWald und Holz und den primären Holz bearbeitenden Industrien, 1994-2008 (1994 = 100).

Diverging regional trends in primary wood processing

The regional shift-share analysis identifies strong *regional divergences in primary wood processing* (Figure 3). The method distinguishes shares in employment trends (total shift: TS) attributable to overall economic conditions (national share: NS), overall trends of an industry (industrial mix: IM) or specific development of a region (regional share: RS). In the industries under study, the NS accounts only for minor portions of the TS. Clearly, the general economy has only a marginal influence and industry specific trends plus regional factors play a far greater role. The IM reflects as well the size of a regional industry and allows for comparisons of scale across the federal states. The RS is the pivotal component, which may turn out as a positive or negative influence on the TS. In a positive case, it mitigates or reverses a negative shift that would have occurred in a regional industry had it matched the overall rate of decline in the branch and the general economy. In a negative case, it further intensifies a regional decline. Thus the RS highlights federal states, which gain (or lose) employees due to locational (dis)advantages.

The *sawmill industry* (Figure 3a) reveals its largest decline of about -5,500 of employees in the state of BY. Remarkably, BW's sawmilling, which is comparable in size to BY (see the IM), loses only -3,200 employees due to a positive RS. Thus BW's decline figures slightly less than NW, and slightly more than Hesse (HE), which is marked by a TS of -63% and the strongest RS. Positive TS, which however remain comparatively weak, are identified in Saxony (SN), Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania (MV), except for Thuringia (TH), which gains 300 or 25%.

The *wood-based panel industry* (Figure 3b) shows an even more contrasting picture of regional trends. NW, the largest state (2008: 5,700, 38% of total), loses -1,800 or -28% developing synchronously to the industry's overall trend (insignificant RS). Likewise BY loses -1,800, which however accounts here for -57% and reveals a dominating impact of regional disadvantages (RS: -1,000). Positive RS with significant effects on the TS are found in Schleswig-Holstein (SH), TH, Brandenburg (BB) and Saxony-Anhalt (SA). In SN, employment even triples (750, 350%) and can almost entirely be attributed to regional conditions.

The shift-share analysis of the federal states suggests *opposite employment tendencies between western and eastern parts* of Germany. A similar pattern marks all three industries: Even though the hub of these industries (i.e. majority of employees) is located in western states, only eastern German states experience a growth in employees due to regional conditions. The TS and RS expressed in relative values (percent deviation in relation to the starting year) offer an indication of the *regional strength* of these opposite trends. During the investigated 1994-2008 period, the western states lose over -18,000 of employees in sawmilling and around -6,300 in wood-based panels. In total, these sum up to -24,000 job losses or -40%. The regional factors (measured through the RS as relative figure) indicate a major role in sawmilling (-36%), but a less important role in wood-based panels (-10%). In contrast, positive shifts in employment in wood processing of eastern states account for a total of merely 1,000 gained jobs (+14%). They reflect a moderate shift in sawmilling (-7%) and a strong shift in wood-based panels (+71%). The RS suggest a dominant role of locational factors influencing these trends, which figure around 32% in sawmilling and 95% in wood-based panels.

A further analysis of these western versus eastern trends indicates also *regionally opposite changes in size structure* of the industries (Figure 4). Here trends of the 1999-2008 period (earlier data not comparable) are categorized according to size classes of small (1-19 employees per plant), medium (20-99) and large (>100) plants. Note that trends of size classes in time series are peculiar, because observed objects (e. g. plants and their employees) can move to other size classes as they evolve during time.

The *sawmill industry's* (Figure 4a) national figures indicate that the

Figure 3. Regional employment shifts of primary wood processing industries across German federal states, 1994-2008; a: Sawmilling (NACE 20.1), b: wood-based panels (NACE 20.2). BB: Brandenburg, BY: Bavaria, BW: Baden-Württemberg, HE: Hesse, MV: Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania, NI: Lower Saxony, NW: North Rhine-Westphalia, RP: Rhineland-Palatinate, SA: Saxony-Anhalt, SH: Schleswig-Holstein, SL: Saarland, SN: Saxony, TH: Thuringia. City states Berlin, Hamburg and Bremen are not considered due to minor size.

Regionale Shifts der Beschäftigung von primären Holz bearbeitenden Industrien nach deutschen Bundesländern, 1994-2008; a: Sägeindustrie (NACE 20.1), b: Holzwerkstoffindustrie (NACE 20.2).

decline in employees occurs mainly in medium (-3,500, -28%) and small-sized businesses (-4,100, -31%), while employment in large plant's remains constant. The structural shift figures 8 percent points gained by large plants in the share of total employment (1999: 29%, 2008: 37%). In the western states the change develops more homogeneously across classes, as large plants decline, too (-1,600, -16%). In contrast, the eastern states see a remarkable structural shift: employment in small and medium plants decline by -900 (-27%), but large plants gain +1,600 (+178%) and obtain a dominant 51% share of total. Still, the overall change accounts for an effective plus of merely +700 jobs (16%) in the east, while the west loses -8,300 (-26%).

The *wood-based panel industry* indicates comparable trends of its size structure (Figure 4b). Again, a considerable decrease in western employment of -7,000 (-37%) is not counterbalanced by a moderate growth of +1,100 (+49%) in the eastern states. The decline in the west relates evenly to all size segments, while the eastern states reveal pronounced stronger employment losses in small plants (-300, -50%) and gains in large plants (+1,400, +79%). As a consequence, small-scale plants become rather insignificant in the east in 2008, which is then dominated by large-scale plants (92% of total).

Figure 4. Regional changes in size structure of primary wood processing industries in Germany, 1999-2008 (employees per plant size class: totals in bold, changes in italics); a: sawmilling (NACE 20.1), b: wood-based panels (NACE 20.2). All territorial and city states of Germany are considered. Calculations based on rounded figures as shown on 1,000 scale.

Regionale Veränderung der Größenstruktur in den primären Holz bearbeitenden Industrien in Deutschland, 1999-2008 (Beschäftigte pro Betriebsgrößenklasse: Gesamtsummen in fett, Veränderung in kursiv); a: Sägeindustrie (NACE 20.1), b: Holzwerkstoffindustrie (NACE 20.2).

Regional employment clusters in geographical space

The exploratory spatial data analysis produces detailed maps of the distribution, trends and regional clustering of wood-based employment (Figures 5). The cartographic design comprises the following thematic layers: Employees per county in 2008 (in absolute numbers) are mapped as proportional circular symbols. Counties with outstanding concentrations are named (motor vehicle licence number). A colour scheme distinguishes employment changes between growing and shrinking locations (1999 to 2008, earlier years not available for counties). Vanishing locations ('extinctions': zero employment in 2008) and new foundations ('origins': zero in 1999) during this period are identified as distinct symbols. The Local Moran's I index maps statistically significant centres of regional clusters, which comprise groups of neighbouring counties with outstanding high levels of employment (agglomeration). The Local Getis-Ord G_i^* index is visualized as a spatial trend surface (interpolated through inverse distance weights) indicating regions of 'cold' and 'hot' agglomeration. Each industry under study reveals a distinct agglomeration pattern.

The *sawmill industry* (Figure 5a) shows a number of clusters dispersed across Germany, mainly located in border regions of the federal states. The largest agglomeration stretches across six neighbouring counties in eastern BW/Franken region (major counties: SHA, AA), comprising 3,300 (12%) of total employees in sawmilling. Other significant agglomerations are situated in western BW/Black Forest (OG), NW/Sauerland (HSK) and eastern BY/Niederbayern (REG). In the eastern German states, where the sawmill structure is dominated by a number of large plants settled in strategic locations (e. g. in close proximity to the Polish border or the Baltic Sea port of Wis-

mar, MV: HWI), only local concentrations occur. Nevertheless, most eastern concentrations indicate positive growth, while the large losses in employees visibly are located in the western parts (e. g. negative hotspots are western BW, northern and eastern BY). Besides, another peculiar pattern can be observed: in several locations throughout Germany large concentrations with positive growth occur, while smaller locations in their vicinity decline or vanish (e. g. NW: BOR/COE, NI: OS, BB: TF, TH: SOK, BW: SHA/AA).

The *wood-based panel industry* (Figure 5b) shows the strongest trend of agglomeration. Employment is largely located in one cluster region uniting seven highly significant counties in NW/Eastern Westphalia, where more than 5,000 employees (30% of total) are concentrated. Besides, numerous concentrations of smaller scale occur in the remaining states, which however may have a considerable local impact (e. g. MV: HWI, SN: RG). While employment declines considerably in the NW cluster (except HSK) and in BW, most other locations reveal growth trends. Again, a pattern of 'large and growing' versus 'small and declining' locations is observable. In many locations, especially notable in BY, enterprises and their employment completely vanished from the map since 1999. On the other hand, several new foundations originated in eastern Germany.

Discussion

An underestimated sector and its future potentials

The EU concept of the forest sector unified by the common resource or commodity wood distinguishes it from other sectors, which are generally formed around a group of similar finished products and are manifest as such in official statistics (e. g. the automobile industry). Although the definition proposed here still captures only part of the cluster's true complexity (e. g. underestimation of forestry and crafts, neglect of non timber forest products), it offers a more complete mapping of the industries involved than commonly used in forest sector studies. Incorporating small scale crafts and trade industries, it extends the original EU concept without losing the benchmarking properties of the referential NACE system. Thus the statistical account of the sector's macroeconomic size represents new key information that is unavailable from the official statistics and enables a direct valuation of the figures within their economic context.

The point of this macroeconomic benchmarking of the national forest cluster is to demonstrate its relative position among other 'major' sectors, which receive much more public attention. Key figures on the largely underestimated size and economic impact of the forest sector in regional contexts are generally not available to industry representatives and political decision makers, owing to the distorted representation of the forest sector in official statistics (i.e. segregated allocation of wood-based industries to separate NACE sections) and a misconception of the whole sector in the industries themselves (i.e. uninformed image, poor sectoral organization and lacking capabilities to represent interests jointly in politics, the media and the public compared to other dominant national sectors).

First of all it has to be noted to what extent today this sector is an established, major force in the employment market within national and regional economies, and of particular importance in rural areas. This adds a crucial socioeconomic perspective to the emerging debate on sustainable development of regional biomass resources for material and energetic uses in the context of global change. Unlike other sectors, it encompasses supply chains from rural primary production to multiple finished products and end uses, which have developed to modern, technologically advanced and environmentally sound industries (e. g. wood-based building, dendroenergy). Second, the cluster is principally based on a natural resource of regional abundance (e. g. Germany holds the largest forest stock in Europe in terms of volume)

Figure 5. Regional clusters of primary wood processing industries in Germany, 1999-2008. a: sawmilling (NACE 20.1), b: wood-based panels (NACE 20.2). Regionalcluster in den primären Holz bearbeitenden Industrien in Deutschland, 1999-2008. a: Sägeindustrie (NACE 20.1), b: Holzwerkstoffindustrie (NACE 20.2).

that is managed in per se long-term production cycles, a decisive strength for more autonomy of international supplies. In times of rising competition among energy suppliers, international markets in turmoil and unseen employment fluctuations in a global economy, the forest cluster offers therefore considerable strengths and opportunities for regional sustainable development. In this sense, forest cluster analysis can provide crucial baseline information for the understanding and formation of a commonly underestimated, yet still rather fragmented sector. Thus, efforts to mobilize political support and public attention for the sector's future potentials may be strengthened.

Regional structural change and the role of federal subsidies

The national forest cluster, and in particular the primary wood processing industries reveal an overall, pronounced decline in employment during the past decade, induced by a national economy in recession and industry-internal concentration processes. The research documents a massive ongoing structural change, which is evidenced by a disproportional decrease compared to the general economic development, by contrasting trends in eastern versus western German states and in small versus large plants. Positive employment trends in the forest sector were identified particularly in eastern German states, which more than 15 years after the German reunification still display

low industrialisation and the highest unemployment rates. The observed trends were primarily a function of regional conditions, i.e. the presence of locational advantages in these states. Federal subsidies for industrial investments, labour costs, land values and infrastructural advantages are suggested to be decisive factors of concern that are likely to have caused the regionally contrasting employment trends in Germany (Klein et al. 2009a).

Especially financial assistance from the federal and states governments (in the context of post-reunification policy on subsidising eastern federal states) targeted a stimulation of economic activity. Numerous enterprises made use of these subsidies to invest in new businesses and/or relocate their production to eastern Germany (Eickelpasch and Pfeiffer 2006). It is known that a number of large-scale wood-based enterprises were subsidised (e. g. MWAT 2006), however, because detailed information about subsidies is subject to privacy laws by the federal government, a statistical correlation to this factor cannot be tested.

Nevertheless, considering the disproportional decline in the forest sector, it can be concluded that federal subsidies could not stimulate overall employment in the sector during the last decade. If at all, they have led to a relocation of wood-based employment resulting in a comparatively weak growth in eastern German states, which could not compensate for the rapid decline in western Germany. Especially in view of these results, which must be seen in the context of a harsh ongoing structural change and market competition in the wood

processing industries, the justification for financial support of large scale plants through federal tax-based subsidies loses its legitimacy from a regional economics perspective.

Subsidised new investments in eastern Germany's wood industry have most often been realised by larger businesses that founded new large-scale, high-tech processing plants. This has led to a dual structure of wood-based industries in eastern Germany characterised by a few large enterprises versus many traditional small-scale enterprises, which encounter problems of low capital, low capacity for innovation and high adjustment pressure (Krätke and Scheuplein 2001). This ongoing structural and technological change in wood processing and manufacturing can be considered an overall trend in a globalised market economy (Sowlati and Vahid 2006), yet it remains very questionable, whether such investments in high-tech, less labour-intense large plants are rightfully co-financed by federal subsidies that are mainly targeted at the reduction of unemployment.

Evidence for wood-based clusters and locational factors

The geostatistical analysis provides an efficient tool to pinpoint wood-based industrial clusters in geographical space and reveal particularly complex and variable distributional patterns. The notable characteristics are that the analysis is independent of higher level administrative units (e. g. states or districts), leading to a precise localisation and delineation, and that it adds geostatistical evidence and proof to the so far solely descriptive information on sectoral clusters in German wood-based industries (Hazley 2000, Mantau et al. 2002, Litzberger 2007).

The outstanding clusters correspond to known hotspot regions of wood industries with large processing capacities, yet so far their regional impact on employment has not been demonstrated explicitly. The mapped regions point out the forest sector's substantial impact on regional and rural economies, a statement that remained largely hypothetical in the literature. In fact, Kies et al. (2009) highlight that the forest sector can even obtain a leading position in regional economies, accounting for nearly 20% of total employment in some German counties, which represents a decisive deviation from the national average of 3%.

It is notable that the observed agglomerations vary considerably in their spatial extent. The predominantly small-sized sawmill industry is characterised by a number of smaller, more disjunctive agglomerations. By contrast, there are only a few (albeit larger) clusters of the wood-based panel industry, indicating a stronger concentration and larger impact on both regional employment and acquisition of resources for production (e. g. raw timber and semi-finished wood products).

Spatial clustering of industries in general (Porter 2000) and of wood-based industries in particular (Young 2007, Aguilar et al. 2009) is generally related to the influence of locational factors. While reducing transportation costs was traditionally seen to play the key role in the establishment of resource-based industries in proximity to their raw materials, it is acknowledged today that an industry's location is determined by a complex set of factors, such as natural endowments, costs and availability of skilled labour, advantageous infrastructure and connection to markets in populated areas, favourable regional policy, concentration trends induced by technological progress and last but not least the local entrepreneurs' abilities.

Recent research points out the importance of centrifugal (dispersive) forces such as undesired competition for resources in the primary wood processing industries (Aguilar 2008). This factor seems to be a plausible driving force behind the identified agglomeration patterns in Germany, in particular the sawmill industry, which clearly reveal regionally separated centres. In western Germany, the particular pattern of large agglomerations that stretch across several neighbour-

ing counties has developed over decades, while in eastern Germany, where the wood industries emerged anew after reunification in 1990, only local hotspots of a few individual plants with large processing capacities occur so far. Secondly, the observable trend pattern of large scale locations crowding out adjacent locations of small scale visualises the harsh cut-throat competition in primary wood processing.

The decisive underlying causes influencing the formation of regional wood-based clusters are of strong interest to further research: besides commonly considered factors in cluster formation, the regional available forests and timber resources doubtlessly play a key role in this resource-based sector, yet their relationship with wood-based locations and employment has not yet been researched in depth from a truly spatial perspective. After all, further insights into wood-based value adding and its effects on the labour market are required to rationalise the debate surrounding increased wood mobilization, which does, as Hagemann et al. (2009) pointed out, not necessarily entail growth in wood-based employment.

In conclusion, this research presents tested methodologies and first-hand case study findings for the econometric study of the forest sector. It contributes further insight into the forest sector's geospatial dimension of size, density and dynamics in geographical space. As a research method generating standardized knowledge about forest sector employment, it can also be considered a suitable component of an evaluation scheme of the forest sector's contribution to socio-economic sustainability and may help to improve existing reporting systems that are often based on underestimated figures. Approaching a more generalized understanding of the forest cluster requires stronger transferability in research and reporting methodologies. Consistent, scalable approaches for cluster analysis are therefore crucial requirements of the research that can and should be used as supportive knowledge in (forest) cluster management and regional development.

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